

USE OF MARKETING STRATEGY AS A FACTOR OF INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF CONSTRUCTION ENTERPRISES

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the issues of increasing the competitiveness of construction enterprises, increasing the sale of construction materials that will bring profit in order to make a profit by increasing the sale of construction materials.

Keywords: construction companies, construction materials, competition, marketing, marketing strategy

Effective use of marketing principles is one of the important tasks faced by construction enterprises in the conditions of the transition of the economy to the path of innovative development.

Marketing principles are a condition, a requirement that reveals the basis of marketing and its essence. "Marketing in construction is the formation of requirements and creation of offers by researching the needs or wants of the human society for construction products and services.

The essence of marketing is to produce goods and provide services to the consumer, and always to target the possibilities of production to market demand. The following basic principles arise from the essence of marketing:

- produce what consumers need;
- working with the means of solving consumer problems, not with the offer

of goods and services to the market;

- product production should be organized after researching needs and demands;
- strengthening the firm's concentration on the final results of production-export activity;
- using a comprehensive approach and targeted program method to achieve the set goals, leading to the formation of a marketing program based on the use of marketing concept tools;
- to apply the strategy and tactics of product production in accordance with the market demand based on the targeted impact at the same time in order to cover all stages of moving the goods to the consumer with marketing;
- targeting the long-term prospects of effective communication based on the prediction of the behavior of goods in the market and the implementation of strategic planning of the enterprise's activities and marketing services;
- taking into account the social and economic factors of production and distribution of goods at all stages of the life cycle of goods;
- remember that the market is primary in relation to the organization and network plan;
- intersectoral coordination and interaction of plans in order to balance supply and demand;
- striving for aggressiveness, aggressiveness, activity in the process of searching and forming the image (reputation) and competitive advantage of the product market or company, in general, the main principles of marketing are knowing the market, adapting to it and influencing the market.

In conclusion, the following basic principles arise from the essence and goals of marketing:

- consumer-oriented principle, that is, the consumer is king;

- the perspective-oriented principle, that is, the subject's activity must be perspective-oriented;
- the principle aimed at achieving the final indicator, that is, increasing market share, profit, etc.

The main principles of marketing mentioned above are in general - knowing the consumer market, adapting to it and influencing the market. Construction companies develop a marketing strategy based on marketing principles. "Marketing strategy is the main program representing the marketing activities of the firm in the target market, which includes the processes of achieving its intended goal by developing and implementing a long-term marketing complex (marketing - MIKS). Separate product, price distribution, sales and communication policies are determined for each market segment. In the construction marketing strategy, it is determined which product (service) the construction enterprise should enter, which market, and when. Thus, the marketing strategy in construction determines ways to achieve the goal of the construction company using its capabilities in the environment (market, macro factors, etc.). General requirements for marketing strategy in construction should lead to:

- a true assessment of the market and one's own opportunities;
- to clarify the set goals;
- to ensure the flexibility of actions (quick adaptation of the situation to change in case of influence of any factor) and others.

If the main goal of construction companies is to make a profit by satisfying consumer demand, to achieve it, it is necessary to increase the sales of profitable building materials and increase their contribution. Increasing the sale of construction materials creates a number of tasks, such as finding sources of construction materials and choosing the most effective among them. These tasks are construction marketing tasks and require the development of a construction

marketing strategy. In this, the process of studying the construction market, studying the sources of supply, studying the conjuncture of each building material belonging to the construction enterprises and making a conclusion is carried out. Marketing strategy in construction is a plan of action of a building materials production company to achieve its goal. Strategic planning determines how the construction organizations of the construction enterprise work, their customers, directions such as price, advertising, and sales. Construction enterprises should follow the following steps in order to start operating on the basis of business plans:

- study of construction market conditions;
- analysis of internal environment;
- forecasting the future prospects of the construction enterprise;
- future risk studies;
- economic justification of the development concept and strategy;
- creating a business plan;
- determination of material resource supply;
- determination of financial results;
- determination of sources of financial resources;
- cost control means developing measures.

The basis of marketing strategy in construction enterprises is:

- the construction market is not the same, it consists of specific classes (segments);
- the construction company can consider the requirements of one or more segments in the market.

But it is always necessary to think about achieving more success in attracting selected market segments (segments);

- construction enterprise can operate independently or in cooperation with other construction enterprises in the market;

- when choosing a marketing tool, it is necessary to consider the use of those that are more compatible and complement each other with mutual tasks. For example, it is recommended to use the product package (wrapping) with the price, the place of sale with the movement of the product, and the communication with consumers;

- it is necessary to take into account the economic situation in all respects when the construction company enters the market.

For example, the state of the general and trade conjuncture, its position with competitors, etc. The most important problem in the development of a marketing strategy is to direct the construction company to profit based on the satisfaction of consumer demand. Today, it can be observed that the trade culture is increasing in the building materials retail trade enterprises operating in the centers of the cities and districts of our country. However, it should be noted that along with the positive results in the provision of trade services in the construction sector, there are also some problems: retail enterprises do not set their sales markup based on the quantity and quality of goods, in some cases they set high prices for goods based on various rumors, etc. . Effective use of the Internet, proper marketing and other types of trade in building materials in the territories of the Republic is a demand of the times. Online trading is a modern type of trading nowadays. Consumers can order and buy the building materials they need through their computers, tablets and mobile phones. The advantage of online retailing is that it saves customers time. At present, in the practice of construction and retail trade enterprises, the correct marketing method has developed relatively widely: direct communication with the customer by various means, which consists in persuading the customer to buy the product. One of the advanced methods of trading is trading through vending machines. Vending machines play an important role in ensuring the socio-economic efficiency of trade, that is, reducing consumer costs in trade, which is important in a consumer-dominated environment. It is an important issue to use vending machines with modern design as in developed

countries. An important factor in ensuring the competitiveness of construction retail trade enterprises and increasing the efficiency of their activity is the expansion of trading with new building materials and provision of round-the-clock sales service to customers. The ways to ensure the success of the advanced methods used in the sale of construction materials in construction trade enterprises are to provide more diverse services to the customer and to reduce the price of construction materials. It is advisable to use them in construction trade enterprises. It is known that the majority of the population of our country lives in rural areas. However, the culture of retail services provided to residents in these areas is much lower than in urban areas. For this reason, in order to improve the supply of construction materials to the rural population, to increase the culture of retail trade, and to create a competitive environment, it is desirable to implement the following:

- creation of a competitive environment among business entities engaged in retail trade and ensuring the implementation of the correct pricing policy and strategy. For this purpose, to revive the activity of the regional offices of the Republic of Uzbekistan "State Committee for Assistance to Privatized Enterprises and Development of Competition";

- regional regional branches of the Chamber of Commerce and Industry provide practical assistance to entrepreneurs in the issues of finding national and foreign partners (negotiations, conclusion of contracts) in order to form building materials resources in construction and retail trade enterprises;

- establishment of services of consulting firms specialized in marketing services and sufficiently qualified to provide advice to employees of construction retail trade enterprises;

- organization of seminars and training courses in order to increase the qualification of construction and retail trade employees in information technologies and advanced trade technologies;

- organization of acquisition of small freight vehicles through leasing from

leasing companies in order to develop the material and technical base of construction and retail trade enterprises, etc.

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